

Hirakata, Japan) for about 6 h, until the dye colored all the xylem vessels red. Seedlings were removed and the excess dye was washed off. Two to three seedlings of each variety were placed in separate 250-ml glass beakers with enough water to immerse the roots. Each beaker was covered with a medially perforated 12-cm-diam plastic petri dish through which the seedling shoots emerged (Fig. 1). A 9-cm-diam Whatman filter paper disc was placed on the petri dish around the base of each seedling, which was enclosed in a cylindrical mylar cage 15 cm high and 9 cm in diam. Ten newly emerged GLH females were introduced into each cage and allowed to feed on seedlings for 24 h. A set of untreated seedlings was infested similarly as a control. The honeydew excreted by GLH females dropped on the filter paper discs and was absorbed. Red honeydew spots on filter paper discs indicated xylem feeding. When filter paper discs from control seedlings were treated with a 0.1% ninhydrin-acetone solution, bluish amino acid spots indicated phloem feeding.

2. Filter paper discs on which GLH honeydew was collected when the insect fed on resistant ASD7 and susceptible TN1 rice varieties. Bluish amino acid spots on ninhydrin-treated filter paper discs, (top) indicate more phloem feeding on TN1, while the encircled red spots on filter paper discs (bottom) indicate more xylem feeding on safranin-treated ASD7 plants, IRRI 1983.

On susceptible TN1, GLH was primarily a phloem feeder, although occasionally it also sucked small quantities of xylem sap (Fig. 2). On resistant ASD7, red honeydew spots indicated the insect switched to xylem feeding. However, the insect also did some phloem feeding, because

there were traces of amino acids in the honeydew.

We are evaluating the efficacy of this technique for determining the feeding habits of other rice leafhoppers and plant-hoppers. □

Occurrence of grain mite *Tarsonemus* sp. in stored rice

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A tarsonemid mite, *Tarsonemus* sp. (Tarsonemidae), was found in stored rice grains (see table). After one month of storage in gunny bags, 1,000 randomly collected grain samples of each cultivar were planted 10/plate in moist 6-cm-diam petri plates after tearing the lemma and palea of each grain. They were incubated at room temperature (26±3°C) for 8 d. Then adult and juvenile populations of mites were counted, using a stage microscope.

Mite populations ranged from 0 to 19.56/grain and varied by cultivar. Ratna had the most mites and Kalinga I and CR1009 were not infested. White tip nematode *Aphelenchoides besseyi* and fungi such as *Alternaria padwickii* and

Population and survival of *Tarsonemus* sp. in stored rice, Cuttack, India

Rice cultivar	No. of mites/grain ^a (adults + juveniles)	Germination ^b (%)		Survival ^c (days)		
		Unsterilized grains	Sterilized grains	S ₁	S ₂	S ₃
Ratna	19.6	86.2	87.0	360	315	360
Jaya	16.3	85.7	82.7	360	315	315
Shakti	12.0	81.0	85.2	270	225	225
CR146-225	9.0	83.2	81.2	225	225	180
CR113-84-2	6.7	84.7	87.2	225	180	180
CR126-27-25	6.1	86.0	86.7	225	180	180
CRM13-3241	4.0	88.7	87.0	225	180	225
JBS508-13-14	3.7	84.7	83.7	225	180	225
CR1014	1.6	81.0	83.2	180	180	180
Kalinga I	0.0	86.5	88.7	—	—	—
CR1009	0.0	84.7	86.0	—	—	—

CD to compare germination percentage of sterilized and nonsterilized grains at 5% = 3.94, 1% = 5.12

^a Mean population in 1,000 grains. ^b Mean germination tested after 45 d of storage. ^c Samples stored under natural storage conditions in CRRRI godown. ^d S₁ = gunny bags, S₂ = ghumma, S₃ = doli.

Fusarium moniliforme were found in grains which contained the mite populations.

In another experiment, under natural storage conditions (27 ± 6°C and 86 ± 8%

RH) the tarsonemid mite lived for 180-360 d in gunny bags, 180-315 d in ghumma (burnt earthen storage containers), and 135-360 d in doli (woven bamboo structure plastered with cow

dung). Survival again varied with cultivar (see table),

We found that mite eggs on Ratna grains were viable even after 6 yr in a refrigerator ($8 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$), and could develop into adults on moist petri plates exposed to room temperature. We reared the mite in controlled conditions on media con-

taining different fungal diets. Mites multiplied vigorously on diets of *Alternaria padwickii*, *Fusarium moniliforme*, and *Curvularia* sp., but did not multiply on *Aspergillus flavus*, *A. niger*, and *Penicillium* spp. The life cycle of the mite is 6-7 d at room temperature ($26 \pm 3^\circ\text{C}$).

Mites were found to migrate from

seeds to seedlings when seeds were sown in small pots. Percent grain germination of mite-infested grains was not adversely affected, but seedlings infested with a large mite population did not live more than 20 d after germination. Detailed studies on biology, bionomics, and etiology of this mite are in progress. □

Chemical control of the rice white leafhopper *Cofana spectra* (Distant)

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White leafhopper *Cofana (Tettigella) spectra* is considered a minor pest of rice, but is becoming more widespread each

year in Tamil Nadu. Nymphs and adults suck the sap from the leaf sheaths and leaves, which causes plants to become stunted and yellow. Severe infestations cause plant death.

We evaluated insecticides (see table) for white leafhopper control in the field using a randomized complete block design with four replications.

TNAU15776/3 was planted at 20- × 15-

cm spacing in 20-m² plots. Leafhopper populations for different treatments were recorded each week by counting insects on 20 randomly selected plants from each plot (see table).

Application of 1.25 kg ai carbofuran granules per hectare at 30 and 60 days after transplanting gave best control (see table). □

Effect of insecticide treatments on *C. spectra*, Coimbatore, India.

Treatment ^a	<i>C. spectra</i> population/20 hills ^b								
	58 DT	65 DT	72 DT	79 DT	86 DT	93 DT	100 DT	107 DT	Mean
Untreated check	9.8 c	9.5 d	13.3 d	12.3 d	10.5 c	11.5 c	10.5 c	10.5 d	18.6 e
Carbofuran granule at 1.25 kg ai/ha, 5 DT	7.0 a	5.8 ab	6.5 c	6.8 bc	6.3 b	4.3 a	4.3 ab	4.0 ab	5.5 c
Carbofuran granule at 1.25 kg ai/ha 30 DT, fb quinalphos spray 0.5 kg ai/ha 50 DT	9.3 bc	8.0 cd	5.8 bc	4.8 ab	5.8 b	4.8 ab	3.5 a	5.3 bc	5.8 cd
Carbofuran granule at 1.25 kg ai/ha 60 DT, fb monocrotophos spray 0.5 kg ai/ha 80 DT	6.8 a	6.3 bc	6.3 c	7.0 c	4.3 ab	4.3 a	5.3 ab	4.3 ab	5.5 ab
Carbofuran granule 1.25 kg ai/ha 5 and 30 DT, fb quinalphos spray 0.5 kg ai/ha 50 DT	7.0 a	6.3 bc	7.5 c	6.5 bc	6.3 b	6.5 b	5.8 b	6.8 c	6.5 d
Carbofuran granule 1.25 kg ai/ha 5 and 60 DT, fb monocrotophos spray 0.5 kg ai/ha 90 DT	8.0 bc	7.8 bcd	5.8 bc	6.0 bc	6.3 b	4.0 a	4.0 ab	3.5 ab	5.6 c
Carbofuran granule 1.25 kg ai/ha 30 and 60 DT	7.3 ab	5.3 a	3.0 a	3.8 a	2.5 a	3.0 a	3.3 a	2.5 a	3.8 a
Carbofuran granule at 1.25 kg ai/ha, fb quinalphos spray 0.5 kg ai/ha 50 DT and monocrotophos spray 0.5 kg ai/ha 80 DT	6.0 a	6.0 bc	4.0 ab	4.5 ab	4.3 ab	4.5 ab	4.8 ab	3.3 ab	4.6 b

^a fb = followed by, DT = days after transplanting. ^b In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level.

Rice thrips outbreak in the Visweswarayya Canal (VC) tract

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Late rains delayed the release of irrigation water from the Krishnaraja Sagar reservoir catchment area in 1983 and

drought and dry weather apparently favored the fast multiplication of rice thrips *Stenchaetothrips biformis* (Bagnall) during the wet season. Thrips severely damaged high yielding rice cultivars planted in the VC tract in Sep.

In a hill, 60 to 70% of the leaves were infested and up to 22 nymphs and 5 adults (av 5 and 1.5) per leaf were record-

ed. Infestation was most severe 10 to 15 d after transplanting and lasted as long as 40 to 45 d.

Application of carbofuran 3G at 0.5 kg ai/ha or foliar application of monocrotophos 40 EC or phosphamidon 100 EC at 0.05% gave good control. After a moderate rainfall during the infestation, the thrips population was reduced. □